

Iron(III)-catalyzed synthesis of dihydropyrimidinones in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation

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An efficient and fast synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidinones from the aldehyde, β -keto ester and urea using ferric chloride hexahydrate as catalyst in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation is described.

In recent times dihydropyrimidinone derivatives¹ have attracted considerable interests because of their important pharmacological properties². Moreover, several marine alkaloids with interesting biological properties also contain the dihydropyrimidinone-5-carboxylate moiety³. Most important among them are the batzelladine alkaloids, which have been found to be potent HIV gp-120-CD4 inhibitors⁴. The first synthesis of this heterocyclic nucleus was carried out by Biginelli⁵ involving one-pot condensation of ethyl acetoacetate, benzaldehyde and urea under strongly acidic conditions. However, serious drawbacks of Biginelli's reaction are the use of strong acid which decomposes some of the acid-sensitive reactants as well as the low yields in the case of substituted aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes⁶. As Biginelli's reaction for the synthesis of dihydropyrimidinone has received renewed interest, several improved procedures have recently been reported⁷⁻⁹.

In continuation of our ongoing programme¹⁰ to develop synthetic protocols utilizing inorganic reagents under microwave irradiation in solvent-free condition, herein we report a solid state method for the synthesis of a variety of dihydropyrimidinones using inorganic reagent, ferric chloride hexahydrate in condensation reaction of ethyl acetoacetate/methyl acetoacetate with urea and various aldehydes under microwave irradiation without any organic solvent. The reactions (Scheme 1) proceed efficiently in high yields (80–97%) at ambient pressure within a very short time (2–6 min) (Table 1). By this method, protic acid like HCl⁸ or solvent like CH₃CN⁹ have been avoided and microwave radiation has been utilized to get the products quickly.

In conclusion, we have developed a much improved modification of Biginelli reaction exploiting ferric chloride hexahydrate as a catalyst without using any protic acid and organic solvent with increased yield, while the reaction time shortened from 18 h to a few minutes under microwave irradiation.

Table 1. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidinones using ferric chloride hexahydrate as a catalyst in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Time min	Yield %	M.p.* °C
1	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂	Et	5	80	152–154 (153–155)
2	C ₆ H ₅	Et	3	97	202–203 (202–204)
3	4-(CH ₃ O)-C ₆ H ₄	Et	6	97	201–202 (201–202)
4	3,4-(OCH ₂ O)-C ₆ H ₃	Et	4	86	188–189 (187–188)
5	4-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	Et	2.5	90	208–209 (207–208.5)
6	4-(OH)-3-(OCH ₃)-C ₆ H ₃	Et	2	85	231–232 (232–233)
7	3-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	Et	3	91	227–228 (226–227.5)
8	C ₆ H ₅	Me	3	92	209–211 (209–212)
9	4-(CH ₃ O)-C ₆ H ₄	Me	6	96	192–194 (192–194)
10	4-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	Me	3.5	92	236–237 (235–237)

*Lit. m.p. in parenthesis.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary on an electrically heated metal block and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were run on Perkin-Elmer FTIR-RXI spectrophotometer, and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (*d*₆-DMSO) on a FT NMR Bruker AM 300L spectrometer operating at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively. The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL-Sanyo, BMO-700T, 2450 MHz, 1200 W).

General procedure : Ethyl acetoacetate/methyl acetoacetate (2 mmol), the appropriate aldehyde (2 mmol),

urea (3 mmol) and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5 mmol) were mixed thoroughly in a 100-ml Erlenmeyer flask and it was placed in an alumina bath (heat sink) inside the microwave oven operating at medium power (600 W) for a specified time (Table 1). After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was poured onto crushed ice (20 g) and stirred for several min. The solid product was filtered, washed with cold water (2×5 ml) and crystallized from hot EtOH. All the products were characterized by IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy and by comparison with m.ps. of the reported compounds.

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